

LANGUAGE USE DISPARITIES IN MALES AND FEMALES' SPEECHES

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Abstract. The purpose of the article is to explore the gender differences in language use in a sociolinguistic perspective, examining whether men and women speak differently and the factors influencing these differences. This study highlights key gender variations in language use, namely, conversational styles, use of politeness and hedges, turn-taking and interruptions, vocabulary and emotional expression, non-verbal communication and body language. The distinctions between the speeches of both genders have been identified with the help of questionnaires. The results have been presented with graphs and figures.

Key words: gender differences, language use, sociolinguistics, conversational styles, politeness, hedges, turn-taking, interruptions, vocabulary, emotional expression, nonverbal communication, body language.

Language is an essential tool for communication. However, the way people use language differs according to the factors, like gender and social status. Language and gender refers to the use of language in male and female speech. "These differences are not only reflected in language use, but also in lifestyles, and attitudes. Gender differences are a common topic in various fields, such as sociolinguistics, psychology and in female study" says researcher Lihong Gu (2013) in her article. This article will discuss the language and gender from sociolinguistic perspective, including key gender variations in the usage of language. According to conversational styles, men tend to use conversation to show status and independence, in contrast women are more likely to use conversation to build and preserve relationship, seeking connections and support through dialogue. Furthermore, studies show that women use politeness forms and hedges more frequently in comparison with men. Sacks, Schegloff and Jefferson have argued that conversational turns cannot be predicted and this idea has been supported by Amani M. Hussein (2020). Our speech, action, and their order cannot be planned fully. Vocabulary and emotional expression also vary between the speeches of males and females. Studies suggest that men tend to speak directly, while women use more expressive and empathetic elements. They rely on gestures, facial expressions to express emotions. Understanding these variations helps us to realize how strongly language and gender is linked.

Survey indicates that research on language and gender began in 1970s due to the influence of sociolinguists and feminist linguists. However, "the science about "Language and gender" was not published till the middle of the 1970s" says Jalal Sa'dullah Hasan (2023). Later, it continued to develop because of the contributions of various scientists, such as Robin Lakoff who published an essay on the topic "Language and Women's Place" in 1975. In her research, she suggests that language indicates and strengthens gender inequality. She also identified the characteristics of women's speech, including

> **Hedges:** using phrases like "kind of," "sort of," "it seems like," "it looks like".

- > **Usage of polite formal words such as:** *"would you mind...", "I would appreciate it if...", "... if you do not mind".*
- > **Usage of Tag questions:** *for example, "You finished your homework, didn't you?"*
- > **Usage of direct quotation:** *men paraphrase more often*
- > **Use adjectives:** *"lovely," "adorable," "divine".*
- > **Use a particular lexicon:** *"women use words for things like colours, men use words for sports".*
- > **Usage of "WH-" imperatives such as;** *"Why are not you doing your homework?"*
- > **Excessive qualifiers:** *for example: "I think that..."*
- > **Offer more excuses:** *"I am sorry, but I think that..."*
- > **Employ modal verbs and phrases such as:** (*"Can," "Would," "should," "I think we should consider his opinion."*)
- > **Usage of more intensifiers :** *"so," "too," "very". For instance; "I am too tired to go out."*
- > **Less often voice their opinion.**
- > **Avoid taboo words and swear words.**

Interestingly, whether men or women speak more is another core question which has caused many heated discussions. According to the results of a study by Drass (1986, pp. 300-301), "men speak more than women". Subsequently, Brizendine (1994) conducted a 45-page study titled *"The Female and Male Brain in Psychiatry."* The results of her research suggest that "women tend to talk three times as much as men." Thus, while it is a common belief that women speak more than men, research on settings such as committee meetings and online discussions has shown that it is not true. Women can be able to talk a lot in informal situations, but they take a secondary role in formal occasions and tend to speak less." Sociolinguists have also studied women's silence in public settings. (Spender, 1980, cited by Xiufang Xia 2013). Later, Cameron and Coats argue that the amount of speaking depends on the situation, people around them as well as the activity they are engaged in. Additionally, there are many rules that speakers should follow during conversations. The most important one is turn-taking. Fishman (1980) mentioned that men tend to overlap more frequently in comparison to women. Because, they try to show their dominance, as they have higher status and power in society than women. In order to identify the turn-taking process and the use of language differently in professional and social settings by males and females, a research has been conducted involving 120 people in Tashkent, Uzbekistan. During the research, anonymous survey was conducted and results have been presented with the help of graphs and charts.

Figure 1

The analysis of the questionnaire has shown that most people believe that men and women have different communication styles in both settings. However, an average vote was given for the usage of language by males and females in certain situations. Importantly, nearly similar percentages of people realize no difference and consider that both genders use language in the same way. (10%-11% respectively).

Figure 2

The figure shows the differences between men and women in the way they take-turns during conversations. 43% of respondents believed that turn-taking depends on context, such as formal vs informal settings. In contrast, just over a third of participants (36%) think that

men interrupt more and dominate conversations. Furthermore, 18% of participants think that women are more likely to take-turns and let others to speak more, while 16% of contributors consider that both genders take-turns equally. Finally, only 8 percentage of participators notice no difference in the way men and women take turns in conversation.

To conclude, while the article includes clear differences in how males and females use language, these disparities are not fixed. Social backgrounds, contexts, individual personalities, character and situation also play a crucial role. So, knowing this can help people to understand each other better, make communication respectful and open for everyone.

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